

Evidence for composite behaviour in electrospun polymer fibres from nanomechanical considerations

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SUMMARY

The elastic modulus of individual electrospun polyvinyl-alcohol (PVA) fibres was measured over a range of diameters using an atomic force microscopy based bending method. The elastic modulus was seen to increase as the fibre diameter decreased. A composite model was fitted to the experimental data by assuming a core-shell structural organisation within the electrospun fibres. The model indicated that the shell of the electrospun fibre is relatively high elastic modulus whereas the core shows bulk-like mechanical behaviour.

Keywords: electrospinning, polymer fibre, nanomechanics, atomic force microscopy

INTRODUCTION

Polymers are frequently spun into fibres for a range of applications. Fibres for a mechanical function should ideally exhibit molecular anisotropy along the principle axis of the fibre. A force applied along the fibre length will therefore cause loading of the polymer chains themselves. High performance polymer fibres such as Kevlar and Dyneema show significant anisotropy that is responsible for mechanical properties approaching theoretical maximum values [1]. The processing required to manufacture these high performance fibres is demanding but is critically related to the dynamic behaviour of the polymer chains during the fibre forming process. While alignment of polymer chains can be achieved in the liquid phase by externally applied force, maintaining this alignment is challenging as the polymer chains will tend to relax to an isotropic state. Increasing the relaxation times of the polymers used during the fibre spinning process is currently employed, such as using liquid crystal polymers with an effective infinite relaxation time for Kevlar or gel spinning for Dyneema fibres.

The proliferation of nanotechnology has seen a number of novel fabrication techniques used to produce fibres with nanoscale geometry. These fibres are particularly important in composite applications as the fibres present a relatively large surface area in which to

bond with a resin matrix. Indeed, mineralized tissue such as bone can be considered as a nanofibre composite and exhibits considerable toughness due to failure at the large interfacial area available around the nanofibres themselves. A number of diverse fabrication methods have been used to make polymer nanofibres including drawing [2], template synthesis [3] and phase separation [4]. Of these techniques, electrospinning [5] is perhaps the most popular. However, electrospun polymer fibres can only be considered as a high performance fibre if substantial structural anisotropy is present. Electrospinning is a simple technique that relies on the build up of electrostatic forces to spin a polymer fibre from a liquid phase, typically a polymer solution although examples of electrospinning from a melt have also been achieved [6, 7]. Injecting the polymer solution into a needle and applying a voltage between the needle and a grounded substrate at some distance away from the needle end achieves spinning from solution. The application of voltage causes a charge build-up within the polymer solution, particularly at the needle tip where the electric field strength is largest. The charge at the end of the needle tip will increase as the voltage increases until, at a critical voltage, the charge repulsion within solution at the end of the needle overcomes the surface tension of the solution resulting in ejection of the solution towards the grounded electrode. This solution ejection shows an initially stable linear jet regime followed by a more diffuse instability region. Importantly, the ejection process allows both the evaporation of the solvent and drawing of the polymer, resulting in the collection of polymer fibres on the grounded substrate. Selection of suitable parameters such as applied voltage, viscosity of the polymer solution and distance between the needle tip and substrate can be used to define the spun fibre diameters although variability in the fibre diameter collected is always observed [5].

A number of tests to measure the mechanical properties of electrospun fibres have been reported in the literature. Individual fibre testing is correctly perceived as being the most direct way of measuring spun fibre mechanical properties but difficulties lie in manipulating and applying loads to individual electrospun fibres where their diameters are sub-micron. Generally, three mechanical testing configurations have been used; bending of a free fibre length, tensile testing of individual fibres and indentation perpendicular to the fibre length. Details of these tests are highlighted in a previous review [8]. A succession of mechanical data has sometimes given conflicting accounts on the effectiveness of the electrospinning process. For example, tensile testing of individual electrospun polycaprolactone (PCL) fibres has shown an increase in the elastic modulus as the fibre diameter decreases [9] whereas other researchers indicate that the elastic modulus of electrospun polyethylene oxide (PEO) is improved when compared to the bulk from thermo-mechanical tests [10] but 3-point bending tests shows little diameter dependence, although considerable scatter in the data limits the effectiveness of these observations [11]. Electrospinning therefore exhibits potential for improving mechanical properties of polymers although the origin of this improvement, which may be slight in some cases, is yet to be understood.

The aims of this paper are to measure the mechanical properties of individual electrospun fibres and use mechanical models to predict the observed mechanical behaviour. Testing of electrospun fibres is carried out using atomic force microscopy in

order to produce quantitative data on the elastic modulus of the spun fibres. Considerations of the diameter dependence on mechanical behaviour and some structural investigations will be explored.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sample Preparation

Electrospinning was performed by first preparing a solution of polyvinyl-alcohol (PVA). PVA powder ($M_w = 85,000\text{-}146,000 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, DH=99%; Sigma-Aldrich) was added to distilled water heated at 80 °C and gently stirred for 3 hours to dissolve the solid material. A variety of PVA solutions with PVA concentrations of 6 to 13 wt/v% were prepared in order to electrospinning fibers with a range of diameters. Polymer fibers were electrospun according to previous work [12] with the spun fibers collected on a standard TEM grid without support film to allow a suspension of the fibre's free length as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Atomic Force Microscope semi-contact image of an individual electrospun PVA fibre bridging a gap on a TEM copper grid.

The location of individual fibres was found by transferring the sample to an Atomic Force Microscope (AFM, NTegra NT-MDT, Rus.) and imaging in a semi-contact mode.

Nanomechanical Testing

Bending of individual fibres was carried out to evaluate their elastic modulus. This was achieved by AFM imaging of the bridging fibre and then applying a force to the centre of the free fibre length by displacing the sample up towards the AFM tip using the z-piezo positioner of the AFM. The force applied to the mid-point of the fibre is found from the product of the measured bending of the AFM cantilever and knowing the spring constant of the cantilever, calibrated using Sader's method [13]. The deflection of the bridging fibre is calculated from the difference between the cantilever bending on

the bridging electrospun fibre and a (non-deformable) silicon substrate as a function of z-piezo distance, shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Plot showing the change in applied force versus z-piezo distance for an AFM tip deforming a bridging electrospun fibre and contacting a silicon substrate. Note that the deflection of the bridging fibre (δ) is found from the difference in the z-piezo distance for the same force applied to the bridging fibre and the substrate.

The elastic modulus of the bridging electrospun PVA fibre can be found by assuming a clamped cylindrical beam thus [14]:

$$E_b = \frac{F}{\delta} \frac{L^3}{192I} \quad \text{Equation 1.}$$

where F is the applied normal force, δ is the deflection at the mid-point of the freely suspended fibre length L , I is the second moment of inertia defined for a cylindrical beam with diameter D_f as $I = \pi D_f^4/64$. The L , D_f values can be determined from AFM images and δ can be obtained from the F - D curves in Figure 2. Equation 1 is effective in obtaining the elastic modulus (E_f) for free length-to-diameter (L/D_f) ratios greater than 16, where the shear deformation can be neglected, and $E_f \approx E_b$. Bending experiments were repeated on electrospun PVA fibres with diameters ranging from around 100nm to over 600nm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The variation of elastic modulus with fibre diameter for a number of electrospun PVA fibres was calculated using AFM bending experiments and Equation 1 above, with results shown in Figure 3 below:

Figure 3. Plot of elastic modulus, measured from AFM bending tests, against electrospun PVA fibre diameter and fit of Equation 2 (dotted line) to data.

The above plot clearly indicates that large PVA fibre diameters have a relatively low elastic modulus of 2-4GPa but this increases to almost 14GPa as the fibre diameter tends to 100nm. It is important to note that the lowest elastic modulus values are comparable to that of bulk dry isotropic PVA, indicating that no swelling of the fibres occurred [15]. The smaller diameters show significant improvements over bulk mechanical behaviour, which appear more pronounced at diameters below 200nm.

Structural investigations were carried out in order to understand if there are significant changes in the polymer chain organization as fibre diameter is varied. A conventional differential scanning calorimeter (DSC, Mettler, UK) was used to examine the melt behaviour of the spun fibres and thus characterize any structural changes that may arise over the differing fibre diameters. The endothermic melting peaks for a range of samples are shown below.

Figure 4. DSC melting thermograms during the first heating scans for the electrospun PVA fibrous mats with different average fibre diameters and a bulk isotropic film prepared from the electrospinning polymer solution. The heating rate was $20^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$.

Since PVA is a semi-crystalline polymer, the crystallinity X_c of each sample can be calculated from $X_c = \Delta H/\Delta H_f$, where ΔH is the melting enthalpy of PVA fibres calculated by numerical integration of the area under the melting peak in the DSC plots. ΔH_f is the melting enthalpy for 100% crystalline PVA and was taken as $138.6 \text{ g}\cdot\text{J}^{-1}$ [16]. The calculated X_c values for all samples lie between 45.0%-46.0% and indicate no significant change of the crystalline structure in the electrospun PVA fibres compared to the bulk film.

It is clear from the nanomechanical results in Figure 3 that relatively large fibre diameters behave as bulk PVA while at least some component of the smaller diameter PVA fibres must increase molecular alignment in order to increase the fibre's elastic modulus. This therefore indicates that the fibres should have some composite behaviour with one component, significant with the larger fibre diameters, being bulk-like whereas the second component should have an enhanced elastic modulus. The electrospun fibres can be modelled as a composite assuming an outer shell and inner core of differing elastic properties, defined as E_c and E_s . The thickness of the shell region t is related to the elastic properties of the fibre and the fibre radius R_f by:

$$\frac{R_f}{E_f} = \frac{t}{E_s} + \frac{R_c}{E_c} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

Where E_f is the elastic modulus of the fibre measured using the AFM bend experiments

in Figure 3. A fit of Equation 2 to the data in Figure 3 gives fitting values of $E_s = 21$ GPa and $t = 34$ nm, using the elastic modulus of the core averaged over the 3 largest fibre diameter values in Figure 3 ($E_c = 2.19$ GPa) and fixing t over all fibre diameters. The value $t = 34$ nm indicates that while this shell region of high elastic modulus is small, the region dictates mechanical performance as the fibre diameter decreases and the shell region becomes a greater proportion of the overall fibre volume. Direct visualization of two different phases is potentially possible using TEM but the sensitivity of polymer crystallinity to intense electron beams will cause degradation of this structure [17]. Moreover, the fitting parameter of $E_s = 21$ GPa is much higher than E_c but consistent with the highest elastic modulus value of ~ 19 GPa measured from the highly drawn PVA film [18]. This indicates that the PVA result is physically viable due to its similarity with maximum literature values of elastic modulus and suggests considerable molecular alignment at the surface of the fibre. The selection of the outer shell region of the electrospun fibre as the higher elastic modulus region is also physically viable as evaporation of the solvent will occur most rapidly at the surface of the liquid jet during the spinning process. Alignment of the polymer chains within the electric field during electrospinning is expected but relaxation of the polymer chains to an isotropic configuration would be detrimental to mechanical function. The rapid evaporation of solvent at the surface of the solidifying fibre could prevent this relaxation and ensure that at least some alignment of uncoiled polymer chains would be present. Thus, the most likely high elastic modulus region would be around the spun fibre surface.

CONCLUSIONS

The elastic modulus of individual electrospun polymer fibres was measured using an AFM bending technique. An increase in the elastic modulus of the PVA fibres with decreasing fibre diameter is observed, which is consistent with some literature and highlights how relatively large fibre diameters behave mechanically as the bulk-like polymer. Structural investigations using DSC indicate that the amount of crystallinity in all samples is constant, suggesting no significant crystal effects on mechanical performance. A composite model is proposed which shows good agreement with the experimental data and states that the outer shell region of the fibre is a high elastic modulus material with the inner core retaining bulk-like properties. Consideration of the electrospinning process suggests that the shell would be the most viable region for an increase in the elastic modulus because of rapid solvent evaporation at the surface of the solidifying fibre restricting any polymer chain relaxation.

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